

Empowering Philanthropy: A Crowdfunding Platform for Transparent and Efficient Fund Allocation

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Abstract

Crowd funding has evolved as a significant instrument for people and associations to create assets for a great many purposes, counting ambitious assignments and social drives. Before long, many individuals of the crowd funding stages that are as of now being used concentrate principally on monetary exchanges, much of the time overlooking the chance of different kinds of commitments also, the support of a few partners. This disregard makes a significant hole in tending to non-financial necessities and including the bigger local area. Current stages too have limits, like restricted partner investment, an absence of straightforwardness, and weakness to deceitful movement. Because of these constraints, we propose a book crowd funding web application that reclassifies the traditional model by embracing variety what's more, inclusivity across the environment. As well as working with money related gifts, our stage integrates the essential elements of directors, NGOs, contributors, and calculated organizations. The capacity to make actual commitments and select among fixed and adaptable financing decisions enables contributors to broaden the range of their help past their monetary means. In the in the meantime, non-administrative associations can send off crusades, search for financing, and work with strategies accomplices to actually disseminate help. Moving unmistakable gifts and keeping up with straightforwardness through continuous updates are basic errands performed by strategies organizations. By encouraging cooperation among assorted partners, our stage tends to the limits of current crowd funding models and offers a far-reaching answer for meet the developing necessities of the local area. Through improved straightforwardness, responsibility, and inclusivity, we plan to catalyze positive social effect and drive significant change in the crowd funding scene.

Keywords: crowdfunding, social impacts, financial donation, stakeholders, funding transparency, policy partners, contributors, collaboration.

INTRODUCTION

A new method of financing that raises money online has emerged in recent years and extends beyond the standard. This type of securing capital is called crowd funding, and it permits adventures and people to settle on an immediate decision by means of the web to general society to fund-raise for imaginative and new ventures. "Crowd funding" describes a method by which financial backing is solicited from the public over a set timeframe through an open online request either as a donation with no expected returns or in exchange for future products or rewards in monetary or other forms. Crowd funding and crowd funding stages contrast essentially in their method of activity. Based on what backers get in return for their contributions, various crowd funding models have been proposed. For example, value shares, an item or administration or other non-money related remunerates pretty much representative or a specific loan fee. These three kinds of crowd funding highlight altogether different methods of activity and are typically dissected independently.

In this study we centre around only one of these kinds by especially breaking down non monetary crowd funding. Non monetary crowd funding contrast in the thought processes of the task initiators and allies and consequently are much of the time portrayed independently in the writing. Distinguishing donation-driven efforts from reward-motivated support proves challenging when put into action. So frequently in individual lobbies for rather low gifts more modest, more representative trade merchandise are offered though in similar mission for rather high reward merchandise with a critical financial worth are advertised. As a result, donation based exchanges are also covered by the majority of reward-based crowd funding platforms and campaigns. Our group financing stage remains as a signal of straightforwardness and trust, rethinking the scene of gathering pledges through creative elements intended to advance responsibility and cultivate certainty among all partners. Continuous following, straightforward correspondence channels, and hearty detailing instruments act as points of support, developing a culture of straightforwardness and trust inside our local area. We accept that by embracing these standards, we prepare for significant coordinated effort and feasible social effect.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the early examination, crowd funding has been analyzed basically regarding legitimate issues and pioneering finance. This literature review dives into several studies that show how technology, nongovernmental organizations, and donors can promote funding platforms.

Pandey et al. (2019) highlighted the loopholes in the Indian charity platforms. The platforms are likely to be involved in risks such as corruption. To solve the security risks and in the view of providing a secured and transparent platform, the authors decided to design a platform using Blockchain technology. The resultant application was designed with a decentralized storage architecture, Distributed Ledger Technology and Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM).

Daventa et al. (2022) studied about the crowd funding platforms in Indonesia. They observed that the majority of crowd funding platforms are used based on emergency cause or need. To expand the application of crowd funding, the authors designed ARtopia, a Mobile Application based crowd funding platform to support artists and content creators seek help when they face copyright and online piracy issues.

Maryani et al. (2020) developed a web- application to facilitate business investors to search according to their interests. The application was designed using Object Oriented Analysis and Design (OOAD) method and notations were implemented using Unified Modelling Language (UML) standard. The preferences of the investors are asked in the form of a survey and the results are given to the user based on their responses.

Sujaritha.M et al. (2022) highlighted the lack of transparency and money control in the crowd funding platform for the investors. There was no proper guarantee that in the existing platform that the money invested is completely used for a cause. Keeping assurance as the main key a decentralized blockchain and smart contract-based application was proposed.

Beier and Wagner (2016) studied user behaviour in the well-known crowd funding platforms in Switzerland. They observed that the target of the campaigns is achieved on the first days of the campaign. The tendency to follow the actions of others, have a notable impact on the success of crowd funding campaigns. To optimize these campaigns, researchers and crowd funding platforms must understand and utilize user behaviour.

Mora and Palos-Sanchez (2023) studied existing crowd funding platforms focusing on the Reward, Equity, and Lending categories to implement a better idea for future needs. The review identified that crowd funding platforms as an alternative for financing are becoming popular. They stressed the importance of future research into technology factors and decision- making processes in crowd fundingecosystems.

Moritz and Block (2014) reviewed the existing crowd funding literature, categorizing it according to some important segments such as capital seekers, providers, and intermediaries. They identified drawbacks in existing research and proposed solutions for future investigation, stressing the importance of understanding the roles and interactions of various users within crowd fundingecosystems.

Lopez-Golan et al. (2016) looked into the possibility of using charity donation to help Ecuadorian filmmakers make movies. They came to know that websites could promote cooperation in the creative arts and increase financing accessibility.

The literature review showcases the evolution and potential of crowd funding, addressing its diverse applications, challenges, and innovative solutions such as blockchain technology and smart contracts, ultimately highlighting the transformative impact these advancements can have on crowd funding platforms and peer-to-peer transactions.

METHODOLOGY

The general target of the objective is to foster an easy-to-understand online stage that overcomes any barrier between humanitarian elements and donors, cultivating straightforward and open correspondence. Focus on an easy to understand connection point to work with consistent communication among Donors, NGOs, Logistics, and Administrators, implement constant following of actual things with geo-labelled photograph updates to furnish contributors with confirmation and transparency, establish a powerful revealing instrument for clients to banner and report counterfeit asset demands, guaranteeing the uprightness of the stage and Guarantee the believability of NGOs, Donors, and coordinated factors accomplices through thorough recordcheck processes during enlistment.

Post Creation: Within this module, users are granted the ability to contribute valuable posts related to Funds. This feature improves the platform's content with multimedia elements and location tags.

Fig_1: Post creation flow diagram

Moderation and Content Integrity: For a satisfying user experience, content integrity must be maintained. This module uses a user-reporting system to handle the issue of inappropriate content. Users can report content that they believe to be improper or that breaks the community's guidelines.

Fig_2: User report system flow diagram

Verification of NGOs and Logistics: In order to maintain integrity of the web application a verification mechanism has been established for NGOs and Logistics.

Fig_3: NGO and Logistics verification flow diagram

Physical Donation and Tracking: Ensuring accurate tracking of donated things and facilitating non-monetary contributions are made possible in large part by the physical donation feature of the crowd funding platform. In this process, logistical firms play a crucial role as they are accountable for transferring physical donations from donors or non-governmental organizations to the designated recipients. Logistics staff can view and manage donation requests after registering and having their accounts verified.

Fig_4: Physical donation and Tracking flow diagram

Campaigns by NGO: NGOs can launch and oversee campaigns for regular funding with the help of the platform. NGOs are essential in solving societal problems and carrying out worthwhile projects, which frequently call for ongoing financial support. NGOs can use the platform to set up targeted campaigns to generate money for the activities that require continuous financial support.

Monetary Donation: The crowd funding platforms monetary donation module makes it easy and safe for donors to contribute money to support the needy. Donors have the flexibility to opt for either fixed or flexible forms of donation according to their convenience.

Fig_5: Monetary donations flow diagram

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the outcomes and conversation segment of the undertaking, discoveries relating to client commitment, gift measurements, confirmation cycles, and venture influence are introduced and broke down. Client commitment measurements, including the quantity of enlisted clients and their movement levels, give experiences into the stage's reception and prevalence among clients.

Fig_6: Homepage of the application

The adequacy of the check interaction for NGOs, business visionaries, and operations accomplices is surveyed through confirmation achievement rates and difficulties experienced. Besides, the effect appraisal assesses the unmistakable results of subsidized projects, displaying examples of overcoming adversity and recipient input. Through translation and conversation of these discoveries, bits of knowledge into client experience, gathering pledges procedures, difficulties, and examples learned are gathered, giving significant bits of knowledge to future upgrades and enhancements to the stage.

Fig_7: Homepage of the application

The landing page UI of our venture fills in as the focal centre for clients to explore and draw in with our humanitarian stage. At the highest point of the page, an unmistakable and instinctive route menu guides clients to key segments, including gift open doors, project postings, client profiles, and correspondence channels. Through thoughtfulness regarding visual plan and marking, the landing page UI conveys our foundation's personality, mission, and obligation to having a constructive outcome.

In our task, NGO contemplations assume a basic part in guaranteeing the general achievement and viability of the stage. These NGOs incorporate factors like execution, security, ease of use, and versatility, which are fundamental for conveying a top-notch client experience.

Execution goals centre around enhancing the stage's speed and responsiveness, guaranteeing fast stacking times and smooth communications for clients. Security goals expect to defend client information and exchanges, carrying out hearty confirmation, encryption, and access control systems to safeguard against unapproved access and information breaks.

HTML and CSS are the integral parameters used for building an eloquent User Interface (UI). HTML is the fountain head; it provides the structure of a webpage. Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) are said to be the enhancers of the HTML elements in an impressive manner by controlling parameters such as layout, colors, fonts, and spacing.

Fig_8: Post creation page of the application

Taking everything into account, our task has effectively overcome any issues between non-governmental organizations and donors, encouraging transparent correspondence and proper asset allotment.

CONCLUSION

The development of the Crowd funding applications offers a unique user experience with diverse user roles, ability to make fixed or flexible forms of donations, maintenance of user integrity with identity verification of NGOs and Logistics post registration, facility to make and track non-monetary donations. With integration of features of social media i.e., making fund request through posts, reporting the fake fund requests ensures a better engagement between users and the application. Ultimately, the Crowd funding application has enormous potential to enable people and organizations to use collective philanthropy to improve society.

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